

EFFECT FACTORS STUDY ON THE PIN LOAD DISTRIBUTION OF MULTI-COUNTERSUNK BOLT COMPOSITE LAMINATE JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

Countersunk bolt composite laminate joints have been widely used in aircraft surface connecting structures because they can improve pin load distributions and keep surface structure smooth. In this study, a finite element model of a multi-countersunk bolt joint is established with ABAQUS software. The tensile performance of a multi-bolt joint of a composite laminate with a metal plate is analyzed. Pin load distributions are calculated. Moreover, the effects of pin clearance, bolt torsion moment, and height ratio on load distribution are analyzed. Result shows that a countersunk bolt can slightly improve load distribution compared with a protruding-head bolt for the composite laminate joints. Pin clearance and bolt stiffness significantly affect load distribution, and an appropriate combination of bolt clearance and bolt stiffness is determined to improve load distribution. In addition, bolt tightening torque and bolt stiffness have slight effects. Finally, the effects of friction and height ratio can be neglected.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aerospace/aircraft structures use fiber-reinforced composite materials, which are typically brittle. These materials have similar properties such as low interlaminar strength and high brittleness. In addition, these properties cause each bolt to have an unequal load state distribution in the entire multi-protruding head bolt joint process from start loading, which always reduces the efficiency of a bolt joint. In general, a protruding bolt joint finds it difficult to comply with aerodynamic performance requirements. Therefore, a countersunk bolt joint is used in aircraft surface connecting structures. Countersunk head bolt composite laminate joints keep the surface structures of aircraft smooth as well as improve pin load distribution and joint efficiency because of the effect of compression of the bolt head inclined plane [1].

Many studies on the mechanical properties of protruding bolt composite laminate joints have been conducted. Such studies have mainly focused on the effects of the single-bolt joint failure mechanism and the analysis of its influencing factors, strength analysis extrusion, high-temperature environment on the performance of a single-bolt joint, as well as pin load distribution in multi-bolt joints and the analysis of its influencing factors [2-9]. However, only a few investigations on the mechanical properties of countersunk bolt composite laminate joints have been reported.

Research in the field of countersunk bolt composite laminate joints has mostly concentrated on single-lap joints [10-17]. Studies show that countersunk bolt joints always result in stress concentration. Stress concentration occurs mainly in the root of a bolt and not in the bolt head section. Therefore, the load-carrying capacity of countersunk bolt joints is relatively low, which causes a structure to be damaged easily. Compared with that of protruding bolt joints, the finite element model of countersunk bolt joints is complex with respect to defining interface and selecting elements.

A few investigations on the mechanical properties of multi-countersunk bolt joints have been reported. These investigations have only focused on fatigue performance. Experimental investigations showed that fatigue damage in multiple countersunk and double-lap composite laminate joints are caused by bolt fracture. Load transfer in countersunk bolt joints is inhomogeneous. Unequal load distribution in the joint is obviously affected by bolt stiffness. Moreover, when bolt stiffness is large, fatigue damage occurs easily[18]. Minimal works on the load distribution of countersunk bolt joints are available.

This study is based on [17], which investigated the tensile property of single-countersunk bolt composite laminate joints. In this study, a finite element model of a multi-countersunk bolt joint is established. Pin load distribution is researched. Furthermore, the effects of pin clearance, bolt torsion moment, countersunk height ratio, etc., on load distribution are analyzed. The main objective of this study is to provide an analytical method and a reference for designing of countersunk bolt composite laminate joints.

2 MULTI-COUNTERSUNK BOLT COMPOSITE LAMINATE JOINT MODELING

Similar to that in [17], the joints were manufactured from a carbon fiber/epoxy material system (T300/QY8911) with quasi-isotropic layups [45/0/-45/90]_{4s}. The composite laminates are 4 mm thick, 36 mm wide, and 150 mm long. The nominal diameter of the countersunk bolt

is 6 mm. The bolts are made from titanium alloy (ML30CrMnSiA) with heads angled at 90°. The metal plate connected to the laminated plate is 18 mm thick and has same length and width as those of the composite laminate plate. The metal plates are modeled with steel, with material constants $E = 200$ GPa, $\nu = 0.3$. A laminate plate and a metal plate are connected in a single lap. The properties of the composite layer material are shown in Table 1.

For comparative analysis, the M6 protruding bolt joints are analyzed. The analysis is the same as that of the countersunk bolt joint case except for the bolt.

Figure 1: Finite element model of three countersunk bolt composite laminate joints

Secondary bending occurs when single-lap joints are tested at a tensile load that are caused by loads in a different plane, which leads to joints producing additional bending moment and normal deformation. Secondary bending is an inherent property of single-lap joints. It changes local stress and strains field. It also affects the strength of a bolt joint. Thus, a single-lap joint is more complex than a double-lap joint [1].

Material property	Value
E_1 /GPa	135
E_2 /GPa	8.8
E_3 /GPa	8.8
G_{12} /GPa	4.47
G_{23} /GPa	3.00
G_{13} /GPa	4.47
μ_{12}	0.33
μ_{23}	0.33
μ_{13}	0.33

Table 1 Properties of T300/QY8911 ply [19]

In the finite element model of countersunk bolt joints, defining the displacement boundary condition and selecting elements have considerable influences on bolt joints. To ensure that the model is correct and effective, the finite element modeling method for multi-countersunk bolt joints is the same as the method for single-bolt joints in [17].

A finite element model is established with ABAQUS software. The model selects reduced integration (C3D8R), which exhibits good bending behavior and can deal with high strength case. However, a large deformation of the element will lead to mesh distortion of the model. Thus, the fully integrated element (C3D8I) is used in the composite laminated plate bolt hole around high-stress areas. C3D8I exhibits better coordination than the element C3D8R used in other regions [13, 20].

Many contact interfaces exist in countersunk bolt joints. The key to the success of the modeling is dealing properly with contact interfaces. The Coulomb friction factor and limited slip hypothesis are used in composite laminates. The metal bolt and laminate plate of the contact are dealt with hard contact. Parts with high stiffness, such as metal plates, are called the master surface; whereas parts with low stiffness, such as composite laminates, are called the slave surface. Master and slave surfaces use different nodes to keep the calculated model converging. The illustration of the master and slave surfaces[11,17] is shown in Figure. 2.

Contact chatter occurs during the calculating process of a model because nodes of the slave surface change repeatedly between open and closed. This constant shift leads to severe discontinuity iterations and calculation misconvergence. Automatic overclosure tolerance must be considered first to solve a case. Second, an unsymmetrical solver and contact stabilization are used to improve calculation convergence. And the effect of the energy dissipated by viscous damping for calculation result is negligible [17].

The metal plate remains encased, and a composite laminate applies load on the plate. The existence of an eccentric shaft layer can lead to a symmetrical stress distribution of the laminate. Thus, the symmetry principle is not used to decrease the size of the model and the calculation scale.

Figure 2: Master and slave surfaces of the countersunk bolt joint model

C3D8R is used in the entire model of multi-countersunk bolt joints.

The bolt connected to the metal plate is assumed to connect perfectly when modeling. This connection has no assembly clearance.

3 CALCULATING PIN LOAD DISTRIBUTION

Experiential research on relevant literature[4] shows that the pin load distribution of multi-countersunk bolt composite laminate joints varies with changing load. However, before serious bolt hole damage appears, the load-displacement curve of specimen tensile presents a linear segment. Moreover, load distribution is roughly uniform in case of a linear segment.

Material damage is ignored during calculation because this study focuses on pin load distribution. In addition, a material is assumed to remain in good condition under the load. In [17], the linear segment of a single-countersunk bolt joint load-displacement curve was found to end at a load of 4.8 kN. The load value of a three-bolt joint must be larger than that of a single-bolt joint. In this case, 8 kN is used.

Four sections shown in Figure. 3 are selected to calculate load distribution.

The normal stress of each section is integrated to obtain their tensile load. The difference in the adjacent load value of a section is the load applied on the bolt, i.e., the transferred load. Meanwhile, the ratio of the load applied on the bolt to the external load is called the pin load distribution ratio.

As shown in Figure. 4, the strain contours of the two kinds (i.e., countersunk and protruding) of bolt composite laminates remain under an 8 kN tensile load regardless of load distribution factors such as bolt clearance, bolt tightening torque, friction, etc. The strain contours of the protruding bolt composite laminate shown in Figure. 4b is in accordance with calculation results in [4]. This result proves the validity of the model.

As illustrated in Figure. 4, the largest strain of the laminate appears at bolt 1. This strain indicates that bolt 1 transfers the largest amount of joint applied load. Bolt 1 of the protruding bolt joint has a bigger large strain zone compared with that of bolt 1 of the countersunk bolt joint. This difference shows that bolt 1 of the protruding bolt joint transfers a larger amount of the applied load than bolt 1 of the countersunk bolt joint.

Figure 3: Selected sections used to calculate pin load

(a): Countersunk bolt composite laminate

(b): Protruding bolt composite laminate

Figure 4: Strain contours of the two kinds of bolt composite laminates

The load distributions of different types of bolt joint are shown in Table 2. The result of the pin load distribution of the protruding bolt joint is the same as that in [4]. Bolt 1 transfers

the largest amount of applied load. The difference in distribution is attributed to bolt 1 being located in the roots of the laminate with relatively low stiffness. And bolt 1 transfers the largest load amount, which is minimally progressive. A countersunk bolt joint slightly improves load distributions than a protruding bolt joint. The transferred load of bolt 1 is reduced by 6%, whereas the transferred loads of bolts 2 and 3 increase. This condition helps improve the load transfer efficiency of a joint.

Bolt type	Pin load ratio/%		
	1	2	3
Countersunk	44.60	31.43	23.97
Protruding	50.60	27.74	21.66

Table 2: Load distributions of different types of bolt joint

4 COUNTERSUNK BOLT JOINT LOAD DISTRIBUTION FACTOR ANALYSIS

Referring to a protruding bolt joint, the pin load distribution of a countersunk bolt joint may be affected by bolt clearance, bolt tightening torque, height ratio, bolt stiffness, metal plate stiffness, and the interface friction factor.

During the calculation analysis, a bolt clearance of 0 mm, bolt tightening torque of 6 N·m, and friction factor of 0.15 are defined as the basic state of the connection.

4.1 Bolt Clearance

Manufacturing and processing bolts and composite laminates involve ensuring fitting tolerance between a bolt and a hole. Bolt-hole clearance may also lead to a non-uniform transferred load, which influences pin load distribution. During modeling analysis, the size of the bolt-hole clearance is simulated by setting the distance between the contact surfaces according to the method presented in [20]. Load distributions with different pin clearances are listed in Table 3.

Pin-hole clearances /mm	Pin load ratio/%		
	1	2	3
0.00	44.60	31.43	23.97
0.02	44.35	31.60	24.05
0.04	44.73	31.08	24.19

Table 3 Load distributions with different pin clearances

As shown in Table 3, load distribution is nearly constant with changing clearance size in a three-bolt hole under the same situation of the initial clearance because regardless of the size of the initial clearance, the contact moments of the three bolts with their corresponding holes are simultaneous. In addition, the effect of load distribution can be ignored. Thus, further studies should be conducted on the difference of the initial clearance of each bolt hole and this case also happens frequently in actual project.

The load distribution of a joint with different bolt clearances is shown in Figure. 5. Load distribution is seriously imbalance under different initial clearances. The bolt with a smaller clearance transfers a larger amount of load than the other bolts because it is the first to come in contact with a hole. Pin load distribution also changes. Therefore, in practical engineering, the requirements (e.g., initial clearance uniformity) for the machining and assembly of composite laminates are high to improve pin load distribution and increase joint transfer load and transfer efficiency.

Figure 5: Load distribution of the joint with different pin clearances

4.2 Bolt Tightening Torque

A bolt tightening torque is generally necessary in structure assembly. A tightening torque can be transferred into bolt pretightening force Q , and load is applied on the surface of a bolt head. The conversion formula for a tightening torque is as follows:[6]

$$Q \approx \frac{T}{0.3D},$$

The load distribution of the joint with different bolt tightening torques (0, 6, and 8 N m) is shown in Figure. 6.

The curves show that bolt tightening torque can improve bolt load distribution. However, the change in the tightening torque, as illustrated, has minimal effect on pin load distribution. In addition, the bolt tightening torque can increase the processing force and friction of the contact surface of the composite laminate. The bolt tightening torque should not be too large; otherwise, the composite laminate around the hole may be prematurely damaged.

4.3 Countersunk Height Ratio

The countersunk height ratio is the ratio of the depth of the countersunk head to the thickness of the laminated plates, which reflects the length of the polished rod bolts. The load distribution of the joint with different bolt height ratios (i.e., 0.5, 0.625, and 0.75) is shown in Figure. 7.

Figure 6: Load distribution of the joint with different bolt torques

Figure 7: Load distribution of the joint with different bolt height ratios

As shown in Figure. 7, the load distribution is non-uniform when the height ratio is 0.625. The height ratio has minimal effect on load distribution. Increasing the height ratio reduces the contact area between the bolt and the hole. This change demonstrates that stress concentration easily appears in joints. In addition, it reduces transferred and applied loads. Thus, a small amount of height ratio will be applied in the joint.

4.4 Bolt Stiffness

Bolt stiffness changes by using different metal materials with size consensus, such as steel, titanium, and aluminum. The load distribution of the joint with five bolt stiffness values is shown in Figure. 8.

Comparing curve 1 with curve 2 in Figure. 8, reducing bolt stiffness will lead to a large unequal load distribution, which changes the rule of load distribution. The other three cases show that different combinations of bolt stiffness values can enhance the uniformity of pin load distribution. When the amount of transferred load with a low-stiffness bolt is large, load distribution can be improved, which is consistent with the actual situation. Therefore, in engineering design, an appropriate combination of bolt stiffness values is determined to improve pin load distribution if the requirements for strength and stiffness are satisfied.

Figure 8: Load distribution of the joint with different bolt stiffness values

4.5 Stiffness of the Metal Plate

The same method is used for the metal plate to change its stiffness. The materials chosen are steel, titanium, and aluminum. The load distribution of the joint with different metal plate stiffness values is shown in Figure. 9.

Figure 9: Load distribution of the joint with different metal plate stiffness values

Thus, the pin load distribution is modified by reducing the stiffness of the metal plate. Consequently, pin load distribution is improved. Pin load distribution is relatively the best with the aluminum alloy plate. Therefore, during structure analysis, an appropriate combination of bolt stiffness values should be determined to improve transfer efficiency provided that the requirements for strength and stiffness are satisfied.

4.6 Contact Friction

Friction between the composite plate and metal plate influences load transfer. However, only a few studies have been conducted on the influence of friction on load distribution. The load distribution of the joint with different coulomb friction factors (i.e., 0, 0.15, and 0.30) is shown in Figure. 10.

Figure 10: Load distribution of the joint with different friction factors

As shown in the figure, the occurrence of friction influences load distribution. However, the effect is not obvious because friction can only transfer a small portion of the load. In addition, changing the friction factor has a negligible effect on load distribution.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The following results are obtained from the finite element modeling calculation of a three-countersunk bolt composite laminate joint.

(1) A countersunk bolt joint has certain effects on improving load distribution unlike a protruding bolt joint. The former can also reduce the transferred load of bolt 1 and the ratio of the transferred load of other bolts.

(2) Bolt clearance obviously influences load distribution. The difference in initial clearance leads to a different bolt contact time with the composite laminate. Thus, when bolt clearance is small, the transferred load is large.

(3) The combination of different bolt stiffness values obviously improves load distribution. A bolt with a large stiffness value generally transfers a large amount of load. During joint analysis, an appropriate combination of bolt stiffness values is determined to improve load distribution.

(4) Different metal plate stiffness values change pin load distribution. An appropriate combination of metal plate stiffness and laminate stiffness values improves the uniformity of pin load distribution.

(5) A bolt tightening torque increases the local compression load of bolts for laminate plates. Increasing contact friction slightly improves load distribution. However, changing the bolt tightening torque minimally affects load distribution.

(6) The friction between a laminate and a metal plate transfers a small part of the load. It also minimally affects load distribution.

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